

CONCEPTUAL FUNDAMENTALS OF PREPARING CHILDREN FOR SOCIAL PROTECTION

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Annotation. The profession of “social work” (social service) in our country is one of the new professions and is of great importance in connection with the need for qualified specialists who carry out professional potential assistance in providing social assistance, care for people, including people in need of social protection, their adaptation to society and their integration.

Keywords: Social work, social protection, development, family and society.

Social work has long been located in the heart of every person, reflected in such qualities as kindness, kindness, kindness, upbringing and humanity. The fact is that these adjectives are given to each other through the soul of humans, passes. Actions aimed at these qualities have taken a significant place in the countries of Europe, India, the Middle East, China, Central Asia to practice and taste Social thoughts and ideas. In particular, in the ancient book “Avesto” (BC IX-VIII centuries), the idea of forming and educating brave, honest, pure, entrepreneurial, enterprising people who struggle for their prosperous life, regardless of their differences in race, language, customs, in order to find justice on earth was put forward.

The Holy book of the religion of Islam is in the surah “Niso” of the Koran Karim “...great attention has been paid to the observance of the rights of orphans, the protection of the rights of small children, vulnerable people and women”, as well as “strengthening the family, putting relatives in place”. Also, the hadith sharifs focused on various aspects of social work, including Jabir ibn Abdullah (may Allah bless him and grant him peace) people say: the Rasulullah (s.a.v.) those who say that “every business that is considered good will be charity” argue.

Chinese Confucius (BC 551-479) in teaching, a noble person has five characteristics. The first is Jen - humanity, the second-I-justice, the third-li- eatery, the fourth-chji-healthy thinking, the fifth-sin- tender. emphasizing that jen - humanity, when tradition comes from justice, justice comes from humanity. Hence, humanity is given as consisting of a sense of empathy, kindness, compassion, love of people, care for them. The five factors brought in the doctrine of Confucius cover the core of the social work carried out today.

Amir Temur (1336-1405) paying great attention to social life, knowing that all his victories in the spheres of social life, politics, economy, management and the military, above all, he was engaged in his own business, and that entrepreneurship was the motto of his own thinking and action, he said, “I am very glad that you are here”..with justice and kindness, I have satisfied myself with the servants of my God. I have mercy on both the sinner and the innocent, and have condemned him for justice. I took a place in the hearts of people with my charitable deeds. Keeping my hopes, hopes and fears among the presidency, with politics and moderation my tour. I have

been merciful to the citizens and subordinates, I have shared gifts to my soldiers,” emphasizing the social work in the period of great entrepreneurship.

At the meeting of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on November 21, 2019, dedicated to the discussion of the priority tasks in the field of social protection of the population, it is noted that “social protection should not only be sufficient with payment of benefits, but also contribute to the “standing” of the needy. In their opinion, social protection implies the need to promote people not only by material support, but also by directing various socio-economic services to the vulnerable strata of the population. To dwell deeper on this aspect, what is social services itself? Also economic servicemen? It is natural that these questions arise. It is worth noting that today all the socio-economic conditions are created in Uzbekistan for every person who enjoys the glorious status of “man”. For example: during the period of the formation of the family: in-depth medical services, the school of brides and grooms, healthy (skring services for mother and baby khomila, medicines, vitamins, potranage services for housewives), medical services for mother and child from the moment of birth, provision of social necessary services, material social security, assistance with children's pensions and others, vaccination, it also includes compulsory involvement of children in pre-school education from a young age in order to make them a perfect human being (in order to support them financially, to release or reduce low-income children from payment fees), full coverage of the school, provision of inclusion to all, provision of them with free food, clothing and books, etc. through socio-economic assistance. According to Y.Habermas, as a result of the development of values, moral rules and norms, which are generally accepted, the society is organized by the interaction of people, the state and society will continue to develop and change. The system of social services is the product of human interaction. Russian researcher L.K.Tereshenko believes that social service is an activity that is carried out among the general public, and it relies on the principles of openness, transparency. The social service is carried out by public administration bodies, entrepreneurs, legal entities, individuals and the non-governmental sector.

In the opinion one of the lawyer scientists D.H.Bakhrakh said: "One of the areas of activity for the purpose of people, as well as the state and society, is service". This concept can be used in different meanings: in the sense of the type of activity of a person, a socio-legal institution, a special system of state bodies. Service-consists of management, carrying out state activities, providing management, providing socio-cultural services to the population. Thus, the concept of "civil servants" unites all those who serve in the central and local bodies of power. As in other countries (and consequently in other languages), the public service is officially called "social service".

The concept of social services is described in the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On social services intended for the elderly, disabled and other socially vulnerable categories of the population".

Specially,

- social services - on the provision of assistance aimed at improving the quality of life of persons (families) living in difficult living conditions, creating opportunities for participation in the life of society on an equal footing with other citizens and (or) increasing opportunities for independently meeting their basic life needs;

- suppliers of social services - organizations of social sphere, social assistance services, non-governmental organizations and individual entrepreneurs providing social services;

- consumers of social services-persons providing social services.

At the meeting of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dedicated to the discussion of priority tasks in the field of social protection of the population on November 21, 2019 "...perhaps, when they said that it was necessary to promote the standing of the needy",

the concept of "Iron notebook", which is being implemented in Uzbekistan during the current pandemic period, and the need to ensure their employment, increase their income through the socio-economic support of families included in the "Iron notebook", as a result of which the activities aimed at achieving the well-being.

So what is "Iron notebook" – it? the question is also natural to be born. In response, "Iron notebook" is a transparent list of families in the neighborhood who need help, who are unemployed, without income in the conditions of quarantine;

"Iron notebook", in turn, will strengthen the joint activities of the chairman of the meetings of citizens with the head of the sector and the region;

7 categories of families in need of maintaining the "Iron defter", including:

- low-income,
- having a disability;
- families in need of social protection;
- the elderly alone;
- permanent unemployed citizens;
- unemployed citizens due to quarantine;
- measures are taken to remove displaced citizens from poverty from severe epidemiological areas.

Responsible personnel shall provide information on the daily work carried out in the "Iron notebook" saxovat.argos.uz through the digital signature key on the site is entered in electronic form. In the absence, at least one member of the family, who has fallen into the "Iron notebook", will be employed this year, through which measures will be taken to remove them from need.

In conclusion, it can be said that in today's conditions, the government of Uzbekistan is aimed at increasing its well - being through the support and protection of the people of all its strength, socio- economic resources.

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